

Corporate Cultures Management towards the Retention of Employees: Case Study Company in Thailand

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Abstract—The objectives of this paper are to explore the corporate cultures management as determinants of employee retention company in Thailand. This study using mixed method methodology. Data collection using questionnaires and in-depth interviews. The statistics used for data analysis were percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics will include. The results show that the corporate management culture is perfect for any organization but it depends on the business and the industry because the situations or circumstances that corporate executives are met is different. Because the finding explained that the employees of the company determine the achievement of value-oriented by the corporate culture and international relations is perceived most value for their organizations. In additional we found the employees perceiving with participation can be interpreted as a positive example, many employees feel that they are part of management because they care about their opinions or ideas related with their work.

Keywords—Corporate culture, employee retention, retention of employees, management approaches.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN nowadays the employee retention is important issue and one of the main concern of human resources strategy. Because the human resource managers now are faced with the challenge of how to maintain their people. Especially the organization now is going to diversification or expansion. There for they are affected by any fluctuations in the global economy. In this situation, the organization cannot deny it and have to maintain the potential employee that come with the highly skilled for their business successful in long-term [1].

The staff is defined as someone who is in a strategic position, or someone who plays a major role for the organization. As well as the employee performance and their talent is in need for rapid expansion of the organization such as the advanced technology skill. However, any changes of manpower requirements are determined by the classic question such what you can helps organizations improve and how to maintain the commitment of their staff.

Considering in national context, retention in employees is an important issue across all industries in Thailand and has been of serious concern to every department manager in

facing an increasing high rate of employee turnover. Business environments have become very competitive all around, thus making skilled employees a major differentiating factor and advantage for an organization. For sure, the retention of critical employees must be one of the topics in an organization management's agenda [2].

A Regulatory Compliance and Enterprise Software Consultancy business is kind of a very unique business in Thailand which has a specialized expertise and professional competency in a particular field or area are highly required, especially for consultants who work and play an important role for an organization. This helps us transition to the interesting problem for this specific research topic in a local context at the beginning because, though an organization provides attractive packages and benefits in attempting to retain its employees, especially, critical, talented and high skilled consultants, still the employees often leave for another opportunity or even a competitor. To this end, the research study aims to focus on one possible issue involving the internal organization's management approaches and corporate cultures in particular. There have been numerous research studies that investigated the factors which influenced employees to either leave or stay with the organizations which many of findings came later into specific discussion and useful in further research studies [3].

Nonetheless, none of them has a specific discussion or conclusion in the influencing of management approaches and corporate cultures and its implication towards employee retention for the Regulatory Compliance and Enterprise Software Consultancy business in particular. This research's objective aims to explore and understand whether or not management approaches and corporate cultures affect employee retention in the Regulatory Compliance and Enterprise Software Consultancy business which to the extent that which ones of the identified management approaches and corporate cultures that most affected employee retention in the said selected industry.

Among the others, a consultancy business pays a high cost of investing in their people either in terms of physical investments or time spending in building up their employee knowledge and competency. Though an organization provides attractive packages and benefits, those critical, talented and high skilled employees, still often leave from one organization to another [4].

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Rather than attractive packages and benefits, the previous research studies have investigated the factors that influenced employees to stay with the organizations and the findings of those possible factors suggested that several management approaches and corporate cultures are relevant. There is also some sense to believe that those findings that are not the direct or straight forward statements mentioning management approaches and corporate cultures, anyhow, there is somewhat an indirect feeling of inferences to management approaches and corporate cultures. Examples of management approaches and corporate cultures inferred by the other factors that influence employees to stay with the organizations such as a lack of recognition (employees are not value), ineffective and unstable leadership, lack of challenges and opportunities, lack of career advancement opportunities, lack of teamwork, not having the opportunities for a flexible work schedule, lack of trust in senior management etc. [5].

For the other factors that are not relevant or seem nonsense for any management approaches and corporate cultures such as training and development, long travel hours, overall job satisfaction, extremely large case and workloads, inadequate client resources, toxic work place environment, the hiring practices and inadequate selection and hiring processes etc., anyhow they tend to have smaller relationships with the employees or consultants who work for a Regulatory

Compliance and Enterprise Software Consultancy business. For instance, long travel hours, which is the distance that an employee has to travel to and from their living place to work or toxic work place environment can take its toll on an employee. This factor tends to have a higher or more significant impact with lower-job level employees who work in the other industries or those whom have a specialized expertise and professional competency in a particular field that are not required, such as operations department employees who work in large factory far away from their living place.

To this end, there is not yet a conclusion or strong evidence whether or not the management approaches and corporate cultures are the keys for employee retention in a Regulatory Compliance and Enterprise Software Consultancy business either for non-consultant or consultant positions. There is a possibility that, rather than management approaches and corporate cultures, the other factors such as training and development or overall job satisfaction etc. are key influences on employee retention. There may be other factors that are more powerful than management approaches and corporate cultures [6].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Management Approaches and Corporate Cultures

The aspect of cost leadership, is neglected from the study. In literature reviews, cost leadership is not suitable for service business, which is unique and depends more on customers' satisfaction.

We found many times that the management approaches or styles and corporate cultures are relevant as either the factors influencing employees to leave from or to stay with organization, either direct or indirect statements. Those factors included teamwork environment, trusting in management, organization culture, an atmosphere and organizational culture of tension and fear, management style corporate culture, leadership that values employees etc.

B. Management Approach (Style)

There are many definitions of management approaches or management styles for instance, management styles are characteristic ways a leader or supervisor in making decisions and the results of those decisions will be relating to their subordinates [7].

Management styles are different and vary from one person to another, by each organization, institution or industry, depending on which of those management styles is relevant or will be involved with. The management styles can be divided into several categories, anyway the most often and agreed categories of management styles are typically these three main categories which are autocratic, paternalistic, and democratic. There could also be sub-categories or even further grouping by type, such as two main management styles of either autocratic or permissive. At the end, it depends on which conceptual model will be applied for. The autocratic management style is a direct dictatorial form of organizational leadership and management, sometimes this style allows followers or subordinates or employees to have some freedom in thinking and performing their work, so called "permissive autocrat", another sub-category of autocratic management style, so called "directive autocrat" which expects all instructions and orders to be followed and executed by followers or subordinates or employees without any feedback or question or input. To the end, the autocratic management style seems to be effective only when apply to the large number of low-level or un-skilled employees for instance, workers in factory etc. or when the time that organization faces any crisis. In such situation, a clear direction or decision from the top leader and management is strongly required [8].

The second category of management style which is paternalistic management style is closed and partly related to the autocratic management style however, the followers or subordinates or employees can be dictatorial when only needed. The leader of paternalistic management style may sometimes pay more attention to the needs of its subordinates or employees in terms of social or morale. However, this management style, the followers or subordinates or employees mostly relate with the leader and management as to a symbolic of father-figure. The leader and management may listen to the opinion, feedback, input and view of followers or subordinates or employees, but the final decision anyway will be on the hand of leader and management. The strong advantage of this management style is it encourages loyalty of employees [9].

The third category of management style described here is democratic management style. This management style seems to be the most flexible one that allows the followers or subordinates or employees in direct participation or, so called two-way management style. The followers or subordinates or employees are involved in decision-making with leader and management. The most important concerns, however, there are limitations because leadership skills, the proper delegation of authority are required, as well as the followers or subordinates or employees themselves must have more sense of responsibility [10].

Corporate culture similar to management approach (style), there are many definitions and many ways to define corporate culture. The corporate culture or organizational culture may refer to the people's behaviors, the way, action or the meaning that people attach to those behaviors within an organization. In several instances, there are the agreements that corporate culture also includes vision, mission, norms, language, values, systems, assumptions, symbols, belief, and habits of the people in organization. Those behaviors typically become into a pattern that the existing members of organization will teach and transfer to the new members of organization. At the end, those transfers will be reflected in the way of people perceiving, feeling, and thinking which also affects to the interaction with each other and stakeholders. The heavily influencing from several factors could make the differentiation in the definitions of corporate culture. Those factors include the industry that the business operates in, the location and organizational geographic, the history events in the past as well as characteristics and personalities of employees in such an organization. The mentioned a short definition of corporate culture that, it as a behavioral control, instilling norms and values that result in "the way things are done around here". Examples of corporate cultures definitions from various studies; The set of values, beliefs, and behavior patterns, or even the share of mental assumptions that form the core identity of organization. Those help in guiding the organizational action and interpretation as well as help in shaping and defining appropriated employees' behavior for the various and different situations. The research suggested that corporate culture is one of the important components of organizational behavior, especially, corporate culture help in trying to understand the context of organization better, and also reflected the way people managing the organization [11].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The mixed quantitative and qualitative approach is chosen for this research study because only a quantitative or high structured based approach might not be suitable with the organizational issue as the quality and depth result of response accessing would not be allowed. Then the quantitative based approach of enquiry through a questionnaire survey and less structured or less directive using a qualitative based approach of semi-structured interviews are used for gathering data in

this research study. Moreover, a diary study is also conducted in this research study for the purpose in supporting and cross-checking the feedback from the questionnaire survey of targeted sample respondents. The qualitative based approach seems to be a better fit for understanding the organizational issues or complex human being reactions and attitudes towards either employee's decision to leave from or stay with the organization [12].

B. Data Collection

The data collection is conducted through a primary resource. The primary data is collected through a questionnaire survey combining with a diary study and an in-depth interview conductive.

C. Sample Respondents

Targeted sample respondents for primary data collection which combines the methodology of a questionnaire survey with a diary study and an in-depth interview conductive are designed to not only have the concluded involvement of employees in an operational level, but also top management leaders of the organization who take control of the overall business operations, organizational objectives and goals as well as business strategies. The rationale behind this combination is because it is good to have another layer of ideas and thoughts regarding the perspectives of top management leaders toward the factors influencing employee retention and its implications within the organization, especially factors contributing to management approaches and corporate cultures. Although various numbers of factors influencing employee retention are identified, management's perspective is generally considered and emphasized more on the factors referred to organizational profitability and stability or the importance of the organizational management, while employees are typically driven and influenced by personal gains such as pay and benefits or extrinsic rewards etc. [13]. The research conceptual framework is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS

A. General Data of Respondents

From table 1, of the samples, 57.4% was female, and more than half of the samples were younger than 30 years, which could be interpreted as that members in the SME service business seemed very new to the business with rather low

experience. The general data of respondents from returned questionnaire survey and diary study as well as semi-structured interview conductive are classified by gender and by detailed positions.

TABLE I
RESPONDENTS PERSONAL DATA FROM QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY AND DIARY STUDY CLASSIFIED BY GENDER

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)
Male	8	27.58
Female	19	65.52
Non-Returned	2	6.90
Total	29	100

The respondents' personal data from questionnaire survey and diary study classified by gender were eight males

TABLE II
QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY TOTAL AVERAGED SCORE SUMMARY

total average scores	Management Approaches				Corporate Cultures				
	directive	supportive	participative	achievement oriented	total	work take value	interpersonal relationship value	individual behavior value	total
percent (%)	3.19	4.63	4.66	3.91	16.39	4.20	4.52	3.78	12.50
	19	28	29	24	100	34	36	30	100

The twenty-seven sets of returned questionnaire surveys indicated the total averaged score of Participative management approach as the highest score or the most common value between four different types of management approach which was twenty nine percent (29%) out of hundred percent, followed by Supportive, Achievement Oriented and Directive,

(27.58%), nineteen females (65.52%) and two of non-returned (6.90%).

The completed answers given are divided and categorized to sub-tables for four different types of management approach and three groups of corporate cultures. The total score for each set of returned questionnaire surveys, divided and categorized by sub-tables, is calculated together with total averaged score and total averaged percentage (Likert Scale of 7 = 100%). The ending result of total averaged scores from each of four different types of management approach and three groups of corporate cultures that represented the most common value among variables are presented in the following [15].

respectively. While corporate culture of Interpersonal Relationship Value represented the highest score or the most common value between three groups of corporate cultures which was thirty six percent (36%) out of hundred percent, follows by Work Task Value and Individual Behavior Value, respectively [16].

TABLE III
DIARY STUDY'S ANSWERS FREQUENCY SUMMARY

total frequency	Management Approaches				Corporate Cultures				
	directive	supportive	participative	achievement oriented	Total frequency	work take value	interpersonal relationship value	individual behavior value	total frequency
percent (%)	30.50	39.67	19.16	45.67	135.00	21.17	77.16	36.67	135.00
	23	29	14	34	100	16	57	27	100

The twenty-seven sets of returned diaries indicated the different results or contrast findings against the questionnaire survey, the total frequency of Achievement Oriented management approach came as the highest score or the most common value between four different types of management approach which was thirty four percent (34%) out of hundred percent, followed by Supportive, Directive and Participative, respectively. While corporate culture of Interpersonal Relationship Value represented the highest score or the most common value between three groups of corporate cultures which was fifty seven percent (57%) out of hundred percent, followed by Individual Behavior Value and Work Task Value, respectively. The results explained that the participants or employees of the case example company determined the management approach of Achievement Oriented and corporate culture of International Relationship Value as the most perceived values for their organization [16].

V. CONCLUSION

From employee's point of view, employees of the case example company perceived Participative management approach as the highest score or the most common value between four different types of management approach, followed by Supportive, Achievement Oriented and Directive, respectively. While corporate culture of Interpersonal Relationship Value represented the highest score or the most common value between three groups of corporate cultures, followed by Work Task Value and Individual Behavior Value, respectively [16]. The results explained that the participants or employees of the case example company determined the management approach of Participative and corporate culture of Interpersonal Relationship Value as the most perceived values for their organization. The employees perceiving of Participative management approach can be interpreted into several positive aspects for instance, the employees feel that

their management values their contributions and goals, care about their opinions or ideas relating to their work task or performance, the management encourages and would like them to get involved in the decision-making process and seek their suggestions and opinions. Furthermore, management wishes to give them the best possible job for which they are qualified as well as take pride in their accomplishments at work or even proud that they are part of the organization etc. As to the same, the employees perceiving corporate culture of Interpersonal Relationship Value can also be interpreted into several positive aspects for instance, rather the organization emphasizes the values of team work performance and respect for people as well as showing fairness and open mind characteristics, the employees feel that help will be available from their organization when they have a problem.[15] The organization cares about their well-being and will understand while accepting any reasonable requests when needed either in terms of work or non-work conditions etc. [14].

The management approaches of Supportive and Participative of the case example company are considering more or exceed on employees favor and from an employee's perspective this should fulfill satisfaction at the work of employees in an organization for most cases already because they work in a friendly environment whereas management shows support, commitment and caring manners possibly either in terms of work or non-work conditions, their contributions and goals, opinions or ideas are also valued by their management etc. however, considering from an organizational management principle, the management approaches of Achievement Oriented and Directive should also be underlying, especially Directive style which was scored as being least important by both employees and management. Even though the directive leader behavior will be most effective when applied to lower-level or large number of unskilled employees but for the case example company, the lack of dictatorial style has been proven. Rather than allow freely styles of Supportive and Participative, closer monitoring and control by management is needed to balance the entire organization, the management may emphasize more on a top down approach, giving stronger direction and retreat or repeat the corporate goals, visions, missions, strategies as well as action plan to its employees from time to time [13].

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